

Interfaces between Cranial Bone and AISI 304 Steel after Long-Term Implantation

Natália Luptáková¹, Václav Dlouhý², Dinara Sobola¹, Stanislava Fintová¹, Adam Weiser¹,
Vladimír Beneš 3rd², Antonín Dlouhý^{1*}

¹ Institute of Physics of Materials, AS CR, v. v. i., Žižkova 513/22, Brno, 61662, Czech Republic

² Department of Neurosurgery, Second Faculty of Medicine, Charles University and University Hospital Motol, V Úvalu 84, Prague, 150 06, Czech Republic

*corresponding author: Antonín Dlouhý, Institute of Physics of Materials, AS CR, v. v. i., Žižkova 513/22, Brno, 61662, Czech Republic, dlouhy@ipm.cz

Abstract

Interfaces between AISI 304 stainless steel screws and cranial bone were investigated after long term implantation lasting for 42 years. Samples containing the interface regions were analysed using state-of-the-art analytical techniques including secondary ion mass, Fourier-transform infrared, Raman and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopies. Local samples for scanning transmission electron microscopy were cut from the interface regions using the focused ion beam technique. A chemical composition across the interface was recorded in length scales covering micrometric and nanometric resolutions and relevant differences were found between peri-implant and the distant cranial bone, indicating generally younger bone tissue in the peri-implant area. Furthermore, the energy dispersive spectroscopy revealed 80 nm thick steel surface layer enriched by oxygen suggesting that the AISI 304 material undergoes a corrosion attack. The attack is associated with a transport of metallic ions, namely ferrous and ferric iron, into the bone layer adjacent to the implant. The results comply with an anticipated interplay between released iron ions and the osteoclast proliferation. The interplay gives rise to an auto-catalytic process in which the iron ions stimulate the osteoclast activity while a formation of fresh bone resorption sites boosts the corrosion process through interactions between acidic osteoclast extracellular compartments and the implant surface. The auto-catalytic process thus may account for an accelerated turnover of the peri-implant bone.

Keywords: stainless steel AISI 304, implant, bio-corrosion, peri-implant bone, remodelling

1. Introduction

Interactions between bone tissue and metallic implants subjected to complex loading and biochemical conditions have been a subject of an intensive research for many decades [1,2]. From a point of view of clinical practice, an interest is mainly motivated by a frequent post-surgery trauma and long-term worsening status of the implants [3]. A metallic implant always represents an element disparate to the environment of the living bone. If not sufficiently inert, the adverse interactions between the implant and the adjacent tissue may lead to the implant rejection in a short term [4]. On the other hand, decades of clinical practice showed that implants can be accepted and function in the bio-environment for many years [5,6]. In view of a future development in the field, positive and negative implantation outcomes need to be fully understood focussing on processes which govern the interactions on micro- and nano-structural length scales [1].

Due to a growth of life expectancy, the implanted materials would be expected to withstand correspondingly longer exposures to the aggressive bio-environments. However, data on the long-term performance of the metallic components implanted into the bone tissues for time periods exceeding 30 years are rather scarce [7]. One reason is that, in a majority of cases, an aseptic loosening of the implants is almost inevitable within 15-20 years after the surgery [8,9]. Moreover, the corresponding studies frequently target situations in which a combination of wear and biochemical corrosion contributes to the osteolysis and the implant failure, like in the case of hip prostheses [10-13]. In order to investigate mainly the long-term effects of the biochemical corrosion in-vivo without intervention of wear, cranial implants may represent a proper research alternative. Nevertheless, concerning long-term data on cranial implants, the state of affairs is similar to the hip prostheses [14-18]. In addition, and in contrast to former studies [7], the local chemical composition at the implant-bone interface can now be reliably characterized with an unprecedented lateral resolution due to an immense development of analytical tools during last two decades [19-21].

As a result of bone remodelling cycles, lineage of cells come into a contact with the metallic interface and become exposed to the inorganic material [22]. In a distant bone (bone far from the metallic interface), a typical bone turnover period (remodelling cycle plus a quiescence period) was estimated as 25 and 4 years for cortical and trabecular bones, respectively [23]. In contrast to the distant bone, the bone turnover at the bone-implant interfaces is less well understood [19]. The literature data suggest that the mutual bone-implant interactions alter both

parts of the system. While the metal surface is subjected to biocorrosion and possibly also wear due to chemical attack and mechanical loadings [24,25], a flux of metallic ions from the implant into the bone tissue may modify bone homeostasis in a complex way [1]. Controversies still exist concerning the interpretation of data acquired by former analytical techniques [7]. Therefore, in the present study, we re-address issues related to the long-term interaction between bone tissue and metallic implants. Our case study focusses on AISI 304 cranial screws which were implanted in the Lamina externa for 42 years and thus were mainly exposed to the biochemical attack with only negligible or no contribution due to mechanical wear. The analysis of the bone-screw interface is performed using the state-of-the-art electron microscopy and spectroscopy techniques.

2. Experimental

2.1 Implanted-explanted material

Interfaces formed between the cranial bone and stainless steel AISI 304 screws, which rested in the bone for 42 years, were investigated. In 1978, the 26 years old patient underwent a special thermolaesion of thalamus. With respect to the year of the surgery and methods available at the time, cutting tools were navigated with stereotactic maps fixed to the patient's head by means of the screws. Before the thermolaesion, the screws were implanted to the frontal, parietal and occipital bone and left in places after the operation, see Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Arrows in the CT images indicate positions in which the navigation screws rested for 42 years. Two bone layers namely Lamina externa (cortical) and Diploe (cancellous) hosted the metallic material. (a) Front view, (b) Side view, (c) Top view.

1 Recently, in the age of 68, the patient exhibited an impairing neurological status and was
2 recommended for an MRI investigation before which the screws were explanted. During the
3 explantation, a special small drill (B - Braun Elan 4) penetrated the Lamina externa and diploe
4 such that the screws were recovered from the former application positions. As it is documented
5 by the CT, light and scanning electron microscopy images shown in Fig. 2, pieces of the cranial
6 bone remained distributed over the explanted screws. In view of different properties exhibited
7 by the individual laminas and diploe [26,27], it is important to highlight that, our focus is on
8 the cortical bone tissue which originally belonged to the Lamina externa. For this bone tissue,
9 we compare characteristics far from the bone-implant interface (distant bone - tissue situated
10 more than about 100 μm from the interface) and close to the interface (peri-implant bone - tissue
11 within an about 100 μm thick layer adjacent to the implant).
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35 Figure 2: (a) A post-operation CT image documenting former locations of screws after their removal together with
36 the surrounding bone. (b) A macroscopic view of the screw imbedded in the bone tissue after being explanted from
37 the cranial bone. (c) Partially detached interfaces between bone and the screw, locations of a good adhesion are
38 indicated by arrows, for further details see text.
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42 2.2 Characterisation methods

43 2.2.1 Metallographic surfaces

44 The screws were divided in halves by an axial cut (a diamond saw Brilliant 220 from Metalco)
45 using water as a coolant. One half of the screw was subsequently mounted into conductive resin
46 (Struers) and flattened on emery papers with a 4000-grit finish. In the next step, the surface was
47 mechanically polished in a vibratory polisher Saphir 330 ATM using a colloidal silica with
48 particle size 50 nm. After the polishing, the surfaces were rinsed several times by a degreasing
49 water solution, ultrasonically cleaned for 5 minutes in the acetone bath and finally rinsed by
50 deionized water and dried in a warm airflow in order to remove any possible contamination by
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1 the cutting and polishing media. The metallographic surfaces were then investigated by a
2 conventional light microscopy (LM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), secondary ion mass
3 spectroscopy (SIMS), Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) and Raman (RS) spectroscopies and
4 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Right after the cutting, the second half of the screw
5 was only cleaned by deionized water without any additional polishing treatment. This part of
6 the screw was inspected for implant-bone interface locations suitable for focused ion beam
7 (FIB) cutting, see the section 2.2.4 for details.
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10 11 12 13 14 2.2.2 SIMS

15 Depth profiles tracing a chemical composition along the interfaces were acquired by SIMS
16 using a dual beam TOF-SIMS5 set-up (IONTOF, Germany). The material was etched away by
17 O_2^+ ions in intervals lasting for 0.13 s. The O_2^+ beam energy and current were, respectively,
18 2 keV and 600 nA and the area of the forming crater was $500 \times 500 \mu m^2$. The etching period was
19 then followed by a period of a chemical analysis. For the chemical analysis, a liquid Bi metal
20 ion gun with a fine-focused primary Bi^+ ion beam was used to knocked out secondary ions from
21 first two monolayers of the fresh surface in the bone and steel parts. The Bi^+ ion beam
22 parameters were 30 keV and 0.1 - 0.3 pA. Duration of the chemical analysis period was 3.6
23 seconds followed by 1 second of resting time before next interface layer was taken away by the
24 O_2^+ beam. In order to avoid effects associated with the original surface and building of crater
25 edges, an analysed volume of $350 \times 350 \times 0.75 \mu m^3$ was situated deep below the metallographic
26 surface and fully inside the crater. In total, the combined action of the two beams resulted in a
27 removal of 15 μm thick layer of the steel part in 12000 seconds. SurfaceLab soft version
28 7.1.124633 (IONTOF, Germany) was used for processing of the chemical data.
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44 2.2.3 Vibrational spectroscopies and XPS

45 The spectroscopies provided insight into chemical bonding at different bone locations. FTIR
46 measurements were performed using a wide band Mercury Cadmium Telluride (MCT) detector
47 (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA) cooled by liquid nitrogen. The MCT detector together with a
48 KBr beam splitter provided a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and a mapping lateral resolution of
49 30 μm . The OPUS 6.0 software from Bruker was employed for data processing. The Raman
50 spectroscopy was carried out using the WITec confocal Raman imaging system, alpha300
51 (WITec, Ulm, Germany). The excitation laser operated at the wavelength of 532 nm and the
52 power of 1 mW. An integration time for one point was 10 sec with a mapping lateral resolution
53 of 1 μm . The map and spectra were processed by the Project FIVE 5.2.3.78 software (WITec,
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Ulm, Germany). An AXIS Supra X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (Kratos Analytical, Manchester, UK) was used with the emission current 15 mA and aperture 110 μm . The general calibration of the spectrometer was performed under ultra-high vacuum conditions utilizing high purity standards, namely a silver line Ag 3d_{5/2} at the energy 368.2 eV, a gold line Au 4f_{7/2} at the energy 84.0 eV and a copper line Cu 2p_{3/2} at the energy 933.0 eV. Furthermore, during the evaluation of each spectrum, the C 1s line was first set at 284.8 eV (C-C bond) and the correctness of the calibration was then rechecked by a position of the O 1s peak at 532 eV. All these steps yielded a correct scale for a subsequent analysis of other binding energies. The data were fitted using Casa XPS software Version 2.3.17PR1.1 (Casa Software Ltd).

2.2.4 Light and electron microscopy

Standard light microscopy (digital microscope Olympus DSX1000), SEM and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) observations were performed. The SEM experiments ran on a dual beam LYRA 3 XMU FEG/SEM-FIB microscope from TESCAN. This microscope is furnished with a FIB facility suitable for cutting of thin lamellae by Ga⁺ ion beam. These thin samples with an estimated volume $10 \times 10 \times 0.012 \mu\text{m}^3$ allow direct STEM observations of the metal-bone interface with a high spatial resolution.

In the present work, a plane of the FIB lamellae with the estimated area $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ was oriented perpendicular to the original surface of the AISI 304 screw as it is indicated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Interface between AISI 304 steel and bone. (a) The circle indicates a location from where the STEM lamella was cut by FIB. (b) A detail showing the STEM lamella before a lift-up. See text for further details.

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Platinum protection layer was deposited on the surface across the transition between the screw and bone prior to the FIB machining. This protection layer prevented the surface structures from any possible damage during the FIB operations. A micromanipulator was used to lift out the lamella and weld it to a copper support which is designed for a placement in STEM sample holders. Subsequent STEM investigations were performed in a JEM-2100 F microscope from JEOL operated at 200 kV with an analytical system AZtec from Oxford Instruments. In order to obtain nanometer resolved chemical data, a fine incident electron probe with a typical size of 0.5 nm was used during the EDS experiments. Quantitative assessment of the selected area diffraction (SAD) data was performed using JEMS [28] and ACC [29] software applications.

3. Results

3.1 SEM observations

As it is demonstrated in the SEM image shown in Fig. 2b and c, the cranial bone tightly fills spaces in the threaded structure. While in some locations the bone fully adheres to the steel and two such locations are marked by an arrow, gaps separating bone from the screw are also observed. The gaps result, most likely, from a shrinkage associated with the humidity loss which the bone tissue suffers during the sample preparation and during the exposure in the ultra-high vacuum inside the SEM column [30].

A SEM image in Fig. 4a characterizes structure of the bone ingrown into two turnings of the screw. The fine topographic contrast in the secondary electron image reveals a lamellar arrangement of the bone forming regular osteons which are generally oriented parallel to the steel surface. A resorption cavity marked by an arrow results from an osteoclast activity and suggests that a standard bone remodelling takes place at the bone-steel interfaces throughout the period of the implantation. Numerous intersections between the canalicular system and the metallographic surface can be detected in the distant bone, while the canaliculi situated in a close proximity of the steel-bone interface seem to be less frequent. Rectangles marked as EDS 1 (yellow) and EDS 2 (red) delimit steel and bone regions from which the EDS signal was collected and analysed. Corresponding EDS charts are shown in Figs. 4b and c and the resulting chemical compositions listed in Table 1. The EDS results show that the screw was fabricated from the stainless steel AISI 304 while the analysed region of the bone is well ossified containing an appropriate amount of calcium and phosphorus.

Figure 4: (a) Parts of the cortical cranial bone threaded in the steel screw, two rectangles (EDS 1 in the steel and EDS 2 in the bone) delimit areas from which the EDS signal was collected. The arrow indicates a resorption cavity. (b) EDS signal from the area EDS 1. (c) EDS signal from the area EDS 2.

Table 1 Local chemical compositions (at%) of the steel screw and bone acquired by EDS during SEM and STEM observations.

method	part	label/figure	C	Na	Mg	O	Si	P	Ca	Cr	Ni	Mn	Fe	Total
SEM/area	steel	EDS 1/Fig. 4	**	*	*	2.6	1.0	*	*	20.2	8.5	1.2	66.6	100.0
STEM/point	steel	EDS 3/***	**	*	*	1.6	1.0	0.1	0.0	19.8	8.5	0.9	68.1	100.0
STEM/point	steel	EDS 4/***	**	*	*	1.6	1.3	0.0	0.1	18.5	9.2	1.5	67.8	100.0
SEM/area	bone	EDS 2/Fig. 4	**	1.0	0.5	79.1	0.4	8.8	10.2	*	*	*	*	100.0
STEM/point	bone	EDS 5/***	**	0.0	0.6	83.2	1.4	9.4	4.4	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.8	100.0
STEM/point	bone	EDS 6/***	**	0.0	0.0	71.7	4.8	11.4	9.2	0.5	0.0	0.1	2.3	100.0

* not detected, ** excluded due to hydrocarbon contamination, *** figure not presented in this study

3.2 Phases and chemical composition in micro- and nano-scale

3.2.1 SIMS

Figure 5 shows SIMS elemental maps collected in a region which covers one screw thread and the ingrown bone. As it is commonly observed, a sputtering efficiency and a related yield of single ions is lower in the bone part as compared to the metallic part [31]. In Fig. 5a, a true chemical signal is presented in a form of data which were integrated over an etching period

between 5400 and 6000 s. Therefore, the integrated values represent an average chemical composition in a slice of material with an approximate thickness 750 nm situated in about 7.1 μm below the original metallographic surface. Apparently, this representation minimizes artefacts associated with a potential near-surface contamination and with a decay of the signal due to the increasing depth of the crater. We note that full depth profiles of Si^+ , Fe^+ , Cr^+ and Mn^+ cation signals are presented in the Supplementary material. In Fig. 5b, the same SIMS signal was posterized in order to highlight locations with a prevalence of the individual elements. Due to irregularities of the interface and associated overlaps between the screw and the bone tissue, the region 1 (grey) mixes the signal from both materials. Figure 5b clearly indicates that there is a region 2 (pink) inside the bone which, besides the common bone forming elements C, Ca and P, also contains Fe and Si in relevant concentrations. These data suggest that the peri-implant bone may host complexes which mix iron and silicon together.

Figure 5: ToF-SIMS maps showing distribution of elements in the transition region between the AISI 304 screw and the cranial bone. Regions 1 and 2 represent, respectively, a steel-bone overlap over the 750 nm thick slice and a bone volume with an increased concentration of iron and silicon. (a) True integrated signal. (b) Posterized signal, see text for further details.

3.2.2 Vibrational spectroscopies

In order to assess the bone age in different positions relative to the bone-implant interface, FTIR experiments were performed with a particular focus on the PO_4 phosphate group as a building block of hydroxyapatite. The bone mineralization through the hydroxyapatite content is known to increase with increasing age of the tissue [32]. A dark area in the light microscopy image shown in Fig. 6a represents the bone ingrown into one thread of the AISI screw (bright area). Three regions 1 - 3 delimited by circles represent, respectively, a distant bone (region 1), an osteon (region 2) and a bone close to the interface (region 3). A map in Fig. 6b covers the full area of Fig. 6a and reveals excitations of phosphate ions $\nu_1, \nu_3 \text{PO}_4^{3-}$, see the corresponding peak

1 situated between carbonate $\nu_2\text{CO}_3^{2-}$ and Amide III peaks in the FTIR spectrum presented in Fig.
 2 6c. In the map, the integrated $\nu_1, \nu_3\text{PO}_4^{3-}$ peak intensities were normalized by the overall FTIR
 3 signal in order to suppress changes in the absorbance due to local surface irregularities. As a
 4 result, the map in Fig. 6b distinguishes mature bone regions, with relatively high PO_4 signal
 5 and thus better mineralized collagen matrix, like a tissue in the position 1, from younger parts
 6 with lower PO_4 content (the osteon in the position 2 and the bone region next to the interface).
 7 We note that the dashed line in Fig. 6b, which represents the interface observed in the
 8 microscopy image shown in Fig. 6a, is not fully consistent with the boundary between the bone
 9 and implant suggested by colours of the map. This is mainly due to a linear interpolation of the
 10 FTIR signal between individual measurement points which were grit-distributed over the bone
 11 part with a grit spacing of $30\ \mu\text{m}$.
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Figure 6: Results of FTIR analysis. (a) The light microscopy image shows the cortical bone (dark area) embedded in one thread of the AISI screw (bright area). Three regions are delimited by circles: 1 - distant bone, 2 - osteon and 3 - peri-implant bone. (b) An intensity map of the integrated PO_4^{3-} peak ($960\text{-}1090\ \text{cm}^{-1}$, see plot in c). (c) Spectral lines corresponding to positions 1, 2 and 3.

Another measure which indicates the bone maturation state is given by the carbonate/phosphate ratio (C/P). In Fig. 6c, both wagging CH_2 and vibrational $\nu_2\text{CO}_3^{2-}$ modes are present in the spectra between peaks of amides. With the aging of the mineral phase, the phosphate in hydroxyapatite crystals is substituted by carbonate and C/P ratio is growing [33,34]. The ratio C/P was calculated from peaks $1020\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (phosphate) and $1410\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (carbonate) after subtracting the backgrounds which yielded values 0.111, 0.106 and 0.099 for the distant bone

1 (position 1), osteon (position 2) and peri-implant bone (position 3), respectively. With respect
2 to the local age of the bone tissue, this result is consistent with the PO₄ data presented in the
3 map of Fig. 6b. Moreover, organic/inorganic ratio was evaluated from peaks 1640 cm⁻¹
4 (collagen, Amide I) and 1020 cm⁻¹ (mineral, ν₃PO₄³⁻). A high share of collagen fibres in the
5 fresh osteon in the position 2 yields the highest organic/inorganic ratio of 0.126. This ratio
6 decreases to 0.117 in the interface area and is the lowest in the distant bone (0.113). Consistent
7 with the foregoing results, the bone tissue next to the interface exhibits lowest mineralization.
8 Finally, a detailed inspection of the FTIR spectra in Fig. 6c shows that all the three investigated
9 regions yield peaks from organic component Amide I (C=O and C-N stretch), Amide II, Amide
10 III (both from N-H bending and C-N stretch) and the overtones of Amide II (Amide A and
11 Amide B) coming from structure of type I collagen [35,36].

12 An area investigated by the Raman spectroscopy is delimited by a blue rectangle in the light
13 microscopy image presented in Fig. 7a. The area covers both the bone (dark) and screw (bright)
14 parts with a particular focus on regions 1 - 3 marked by small squares. A normalized intensity
15 of the phosphate peak at 961 cm⁻¹ is mapped in Fig. 7b; for the peak position see spectra
16 presented in Fig. 7d. Similarly, the amino acid proline peak (Pro at 814 cm⁻¹) gave rise to the
17 map shown in Fig. 7c. Consistent with the results of the FTIR spectroscopy, the distant bone in
18 the position 1, with relatively high PO₄ level in the map of Fig. 7b, exhibits higher collagen
19 mineralization as compared to other parts with lower PO₄ content (like the lacuna in the position
20 2 and the peri-implant bone in the position 3). This can be further documented by the local
21 intensities in the indicated positions where the background-corrected heights of the ν₁PO₄³⁻
22 peak are, 0.84, 0.52 and 0.61 for positions 1, 2 and 3, respectively. Interestingly, the high
23 intensity of the Pro peak in the interface region, see the map in Fig. 7c, may indicate a higher
24 osteoblast activity since this amino acid is expected to promote the osteoblast differentiation
25 [37]. Besides phosphate and Pro peaks, the three spectra in Fig. 7d share many common peaks
26 of inorganic and organic components, e.g. the ν₁CO₃²⁻, δ - CH₂ and amide I and III. Finally, an
27 increase of residual fluorescence background observed for the lacunae in the position 2 can be
28 attributed to higher organic content, while a presence of iron ions may account for the same
29 feature in the case of the interface spectrum in the position 3 [38].

Figure 7: Results of Raman spectroscopy. (a) A blue rectangle in the light microscopy image marks the analysed area in the bone (dark contrast) and in one thread of the AISI screw (bright contrast). Three regions are delimited by small squares: region 1 - distant bone, region 2 - lacuna and region 3 - peri-implant bone. (b) An intensity map of integrated $\nu_1\text{PO}_4^{3-}$ peak (961 cm^{-1} , see plot in d). (c) An intensity map of the integrated Pro peak (814 cm^{-1} , see plot in d). (d) Spectral lines corresponding to positions 1, 2 and 3.

3.3 STEM

3.3.1 SAD

A thin STEM lamella shown in the upper right inset of Fig. 8a was prepared by the FIB technique, see also Fig. 3. The magnified view in Fig. 8a zooms-in the area delimited by the red ellipse where a bone tissue directly adheres to the AISI 304 steel implant. Yellow circles indicate positions of SAD experiments. We note that, as a result of processing conditions, the AISI 304 screws exhibit an ultrafine grain microstructure with a typical crystallite size of the order of 100 nm. Consequently, setting the aperture of 500 nm at the position SAD 1, the diffracted intensity forms a powder-like pattern presented in Fig. 8b. JEMS simulations were performed based on the austenite structure file (ICSD no. 53449) in order to fit the experimental SAD 1 pattern with a set of calculated powder diffraction rings. Figure 8c documents an excellent match between the experimental intensities and the fitted rings (red). This procedure thus enabled an exact calibration of the TEM camera length, a step important for subsequent analyses of diffraction intensities collected from regions SAD 2 and 3. These experimental patterns are presented in Figs. 8d and g, respectively. As it can be seen in Fig. 8a, the SAD 2

1 was acquired from the calcified bone whereas the SAD 3 originated from the yet collagenous
 2 region not enriched by the mineral components. The aperture size used for the diffractions SAD
 3 2 and 3 was reduced down to 150 nm in order to target exclusively these specific bone locations.
 4 Several inorganic phases were considered in order to compare experimental SAD 2 and 3 data
 5 to the corresponding JEMS simulations. Out of the testing set, only two best fitting calculation
 6 outputs are shown in Figs 8e and f (SAD 2) and h and i (SAD 3). These best fitting models were
 7 obtained for the hexagonal hydroxyapatite $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ (Figs. 8e and h, ICSD structure file
 8 no. 151939) and the orthorhombic FeSi_2 phase (Figs. 8f and i, ICSD structure file no. 9119).
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Figure 8: (a) STEM image of the FIBed lamella which covers the interface region between cranial bone and the AISI 304 steel screw. Positions of the SAD and EDS line experiments are indicated. (b) Experimental SAD1 from

1 the position 1 in the steel screw. (c) SAD1 complemented with JEMS-simulated diffraction rings (red). (d)
2 Experimental SAD2 from the position 2 in the calcified bone. (e,f) SAD2 complemented with JEMS-simulated
3 diffraction rings (red). (g) Experimental SAD3 from the position 3 in the uncalcified tissue. (h,i) SAD3
4 complemented with JEMS-simulated diffraction rings (red). See text for further details.
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8 We can conclude that the SAD 2 from the calcified bone can be satisfactorily accounted for by
9 the hydroxyapatite model. Nevertheless, the orthorhombic FeSi_2 model can also rationalize a
10 considerable part of the SAD 2 diffracted intensity. Conversely, the situation is less clear for
11 the SAD 3 which exhibits features typical for an electron scattering from amorphous materials.
12 Only one faint ring can be observed in Fig. 8g which can be accounted for by (123) and (004)
13 reflections from the hexagonal phase, or equivalently, by (040) and (114) reflections from the
14 orthorhombic phase. This suggests that already the collagenous part of the bone may contain
15 either some precursors of the hydroxyapatite or Fe-Si residues formed by ions resolved from
16 the implant material during the remodelling cycles.
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26 3.3.2 EDS

27 The SAD results presented in Fig. 8 are consistent with local chemical compositions sampled
28 by the EDS scans along lines 1 and 2 in Fig 8a, see the corresponding EDS charts in Fig. 9. The
29 chemical composition (at%) recorded along the line 1 is shown in Figs. 9a. Here, oxygen is a
30 dominant element in the bone part where also other elements typical for the mineralized bone,
31 namely calcium, phosphorus and locally also carbon, are clearly detected. Slightly surprising is
32 a rather high silicon content, locally exceeding 10 at%, and also a concentration of iron which
33 oscillates in a range 1 - 3 at%. A region, which mixes bone and steel compositions, spans over
34 about 70 nm and results from a bone-implant overlap schematically illustrated in the lower-left
35 inset of Fig. 8a. Finally, clear gradients of Fe and O in the steel part (highlighted by light-grey
36 triangles) suggest that approximately 80 nm thick steel layer has been modified by the bio-
37 environment attack and, in the same time, released some amount of iron ions in either Fe^{2+}
38 (ferrous) or Fe^{3+} (ferric) form into the bone tissue [24,25,39-47]. Figure 9b shows a zoom-in
39 part of the EDS chart acquired along the line 1 in the bone only. Corresponding elemental
40 distributions suggests that there is a correlation between silicon and iron signal, both elements
41 accumulating in similar locations along the testing line, see the double-headed arrows in Fig.
42 9b. Compositional differences between the implant, mineralized and yet unmineralized parts of
43 the bone were sampled by the line 2. High carbon content combined with oxygen and nitrogen
44 in the unmineralized part of the bone points to the presence of collagen, see Fig. 9c. However,
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in this collagenous tissue we have detected again a rather high concentration of silicon which is still present in the calcified part of bone right at the interface and, similar to the line 1 analysis, correlates with the elevated signal of iron. Remaining features of the line 2 analysis, namely the mixed signals over the overlap region and the Fe and O gradients in the steel implant are fully comparable to the analysis along the line 1. Finally, in order to assess a ratio between the silicon and oxygen in the unmineralized part of the bone (line 2 analysis), we have suspended the carbon signal and plotted the result in Fig. 9d. We note that the Si/O ratio is not far from 2 which may indicate presence of silica in the uncalcified bone matrix close to the interface.

Figure 9: EDS line analyses taken across the bone-AISI implant interface. Positions of the individual lines are marked in Fig. 8a. (a) The line 1 samples chemical composition in a transition the implant and the calcified bone. (b) A zoom-in part of the EDS chart presented in a) which focuses only on the bone region. Correlations between Si and Fe signals are highlighted by double-headed arrows. (c) Chemical composition recorded along the line 2 taken through implant, calcified and uncalcified segments of the bone. (d) The same chart as in (c) which better reveals the Si/O ratio under the condition of the missing carbon signal.

3.4 XPS

Since binding energies of electrons sensitively reflect chemical environments of atoms, XPS proved to be efficient at identifying chemical bonds in the bone tissue [48]. Similar to the FTIR and Raman spectroscopies, a nature of silicon and phosphorus bonds was investigated by XPS in two locations, the distant and peri-implant bone. Consistent with the EDS data shown in Fig 9d, a deconvolution of the Si 2p peak presented in Fig. 10 a and b indicates that the peri-implant

bone near the interface (Fig. 10 a) contains considerably higher percentage of silica as compared to the bone area far from the interface (Fig. 10 b). This is in line with the reported effect of silica-substituted hydroxyapatite on the remodelling processes at the bone-implant interface [49]. A deconvolution of the P 2p XPS peak shown in Fig. 10 c and d characterizes a bond state of phosphorus atoms in the implant-bone interface region (Fig. 10 c) and in the distant bone (Fig. 10 d).

Figure 10: Deconvolutions of the XPS peaks based on characteristic binding energies and corresponding chemical environments. (a, b) Si 2p XPS signal from (a) interface and (b) distant bone. (c, d) P 2p XPS signal from (c) interface and (d) distant bone.

The analysis of peaks reveals a presence and relative contributions of monohydrogenphosphate (HPO_4^{2-}), dihydrogenphosphate (H_2PO_4^-) and phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) ions. As compared to the peri-implant bone, higher content of PO_4^{3-} ions in the distant bone indicates higher share of crystalline hydroxyapatite. In line with previous studies [50], a high signal due to the HPO_4^{2-} ions in both regions suggests that the hydroxyapatite internal crystalline core is covered by an amorphous layer in which the HPO_4^{2-} ions are concentrated. In the same time, the HPO_4^{2-} ions promote buffering of blood together with H_2PO_4^- ions which are all adsorbed by the implant surfaces during the contact with body fluids [51]. Furthermore, XPS spectra shown in Fig. 11 suggest that iron ions are presented not only in the explanted screw (Fig. 11a) but also in the bone section close to the implant interface (Fig. 11b) and in the distant bone (Fig. 11c). The iron atoms are involved in electron transport processes, they may outbalance the bone remodelling process in favour of the osteoclast mediated resorption which, under conditions of a strong iron overload, may result in a bone loss and fractures [41]. The $\text{Fe}2p_{3/2}$ spectra show presence of both Fe^{3+} by strong oxide peak at 714 eV and evidence of Fe^{2+} ions by peak at 712 eV and satellite peak at 716 eV [52,53]. A slight shift of peak 710-711 eV to smaller binding energy at the interface area could belong to Fe-Si binary oxides [54,55]. Peak at 709eV correspond to non-stoichiometric iron oxides [56].

Figure 11: Ferrous and ferric iron ions were detected in all the three locations investigated by the XPS technique: (a) explanted screw, (b) interface region and (c) peri-implant bone. After deconvolution, the $\text{Fe}2p_{3/2}$ spectra show relative contributions of the individual ions and Fe-Si-O and Fe-O clusters.

4. Discussion

A combination of FTIR, RS and XPS analytical techniques used in the present study revealed systematically different bone chemical compositions close to and far from the implanted AISI 304 screws. All the three spectroscopy methods independently, but consistently, detected a lower signal generated by the PO₄ groups, and consequently lower bone mineralization [32, 34], in a layer extending up to 50 μm from the implant surface. In what follows, we refer this bone portion as the interface bone layer (IBL). An incomplete mineralization was also detected in the osteon situated next to the IBL, see e.g. Fig. 6b. As it is commonly acknowledged, the increasing bone age scales positively with the PO₄ level [32,57,58]. Therefore, the systematically lower PO₄ signal in the IBL indicates that these regions host, in average, younger bone tissue as compared to the bone parts situated distantly from the implant. This conclusion receives further experimental support both, collected in the present study and presented so far in the literature. The data summarized in the section 3.2.2. document increasing carbonate-to-phosphate ratio with increasing distance from the interface. In line with the evidence presented in the literature [33,34], this confirms the local bone age distribution inferred from the intensity of the PO₄ signal. Interestingly, similar variation in the local tissue age was reported by Shah and co-authors [59] who investigated differences in a number of canaliculi per one osteocyte lacuna and found “less aged” tissue adjacent to the implant surface. Another signature indicating the lower bone age in the IBL was presented by the STEM image in Fig. 9 showing yet uncalcified tissue in a direct contact with the implant. Finally, the higher intensity of the Proline peak in the Raman spectra obtained from the IBL, see Fig. 7, suggests a higher activity of osteoblast cells and higher content of the organic matrix [19,37].

A bone segment age is critically dependent on the frequency of the remodelling events in a particular bone location. A higher frequency of the remodelling events is expected when either the bone tissue suffers from excessively high mechanical loadings generating damage in a form of microcracks, or contrary, when it is in a “disuse state” [60]. Apparently, neither of the two cases applies in the present study. First, the IBL tissue was hardly subjected to excessive mechanical loadings since it surrounded implants which rested quietly in the cranial bone for more than 42 years. Like the distant bone, the IBL does not exhibit any relevant signs of metallosis [61] or an increased level of microdamage [62]. Second, in a situation of the excessively low mechanical loadings (or the “disuse state”), the tissue in the IBL should be

1 fully equivalent to the bone far from the interface. In such situation, the higher frequency of the
 2 remodelling events, and thus younger bone, would be observed not only in the IBL but also
 3 farther from the interface.
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 7 The resorption part of the remodelling cycle mediated by osteoclast cells is associated with an
 8 acidic attack which accelerates a transition of the metallic ions from the steel screw into the
 9 bone tissue [24]. During the long-term implantation, individual surface locations of the screws
 10 experience several local remodelling events and thus are exposed to several acidic attacks. Their
 11 average number and time T_C between two bone remodelling cycles at the same interface
 12 position can be estimated based on a thickness of the implant layer $h_{exp} = 8 \cdot 10^{-8}$ m affected by
 13 corrosion, see Fig. 9. Pardo et al. investigated the AISI 304 steel corrosion in 3.5M H₂SO₄ (pH
 14 of -0.85) at 25 and 50°C [63]. Their data yield the rate of $3.18 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m day⁻¹ by means of which
 15 the affected surface layer grows at 37°C. We assume that the weak bio-corrosion of the AISI
 16 304 implant is mainly due to a direct contact established between osteoclast annular sealing
 17 zones and the implant surfaces during the bone resorption periods, see Fig. 4a. With respect to
 18 a moderate acidity inside the sealing zones (pH about 5, see [64,65]), the corrosion rates
 19 reported by Pardo et al. must be modified using a ratio $1.43 \cdot 10^{-6}$ between molarities of H⁺ ions
 20 in the osteoclast compartments and in the Pardo's solution [63]. As a result, the corrosion rate
 21 caused by a direct contact between multinucleated osteoclast cells and the implant surface is
 22 expected to decrease to $\dot{h}_{corr} = 4.55 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m day⁻¹. In their review, Kenkre and Bassett [66]
 23 summarized data on time intervals which characterize individual phases of the bone
 24 remodelling cycle. In particular, they indicated that the bone resorption phase typically requires
 25 a time period of $t_{res} = 14$ days. Knowing these parameters, an average number N_{rem} of
 26 remodelling events occurring at a particular interface location over the total time of $T_{tot} = 42$
 27 years during which the implant rested in the cranial bone can be estimated from the equation
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$$50 \quad \dot{h}_{corr} \cdot N_{rem} \cdot t_{res} = h_{exp} \quad (1)$$

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 53 which yields $N_{rem} = 12.6$. Finally, the average time period T_C can be calculated as
 54 $T_C = T_{tot} / N_{rem} = 3.3$ years. In passing we note that these estimates are in very good agreement
 55 with the data yielded by the statistical analysis, see the section 2 of the Supplementary material.
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1 Therefore, we anticipate that the higher remodelling frequency is associated with a mild
2 corrosion of the AISI 304 steel implants and related influx of metallic ions into the IBL.
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5 Experiments with iron overloaded mice indicated the high bone turnover, which was present in
6 both males and females in a range of animal ages [67]. Our SIMS and EDS analytical techniques
7 clearly documented an accumulation of metallic elements, particularly iron, in the peri-implant
8 bone. In the same time, the high-resolution EDS revealed the increased oxygen level in about
9 80 nm thick interface layer of the implant, see Figs. 5 and 9. There is an ample evidence in the
10 literature showing that an excess of iron ions stimulates osteoclast precursor's proliferation and
11 differentiation and the activity of mature osteoclasts leading to an accelerated bone resorption
12 [42,68-70]. In this respect, in vitro studies have shown that human osteoclasts can corrode
13 stainless steel leading to the production of metal ions [24] while traces of cellular activities are
14 left behind on surfaces of metal orthopaedic explants [25]. The osteoclast cells are known to
15 increase the acidity within their extracellular compartments to pH about 5, using proton pumps
16 located in the basolateral membrane [71,72]. Some of the extracellular compartments establish
17 a direct contact to the implant surface and thus accelerate considerably the transfer of Fe^{n+} ions
18 into the bio-environment. Under an assumption that concentration gradients drive a migration
19 of the metallic ions through the bone tissue [73], we have formulated a simple model which
20 accounts for an accumulation of the ions in the IBL, see the section 3 in the Supplementary
21 material. As can be shown by the integration of concentration profiles plotted in Fig. S5, nearly
22 60% of the metallic ions dissolved at the resorption site during one hour remain in about 150
23 μm thick interface bone layer. A time domain of one hour seems to be sufficient for a significant
24 transport of iron ions into the interior of cells [74].
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44 Putting all the experimental data and the numerical results together, we suggest that the higher
45 turnover rate in the IBL is governed by an auto-catalytic process in which the higher
46 concentration of Fe^{n+} ions released from the implant stimulates the osteoclast activity while the
47 associated higher number of fresh resorption sites, in turn, promotes the implant corrosion and
48 enriches the IBL by a surplus of the Fe^{n+} ions. A brief estimate suggests that the IBL underwent
49 between 12-13 remodelling cycles during 42 years implementation of the AISI 304 screws.
50 Since this would correspond to about 3 years turnover period, we may conclude that the
51 turnover of the peri-implant bone was accelerated to about three times with respect to the cranial
52 bone far from the implant. The calculation was based on known corrosion rates of the AISI 304
53 steel [63] and the thickness of the implant layer enriched by oxygen as detected by the EDS
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1 technique, see Fig. 9. Concerning the iron transfer from the implant into the bone tissue, another
2 interesting experimental result presented in Fig. 9b indicates a correlation between chemical
3 signals of iron and silicon. Since silicon is an essential mineral for the bone formation [75,76]
4 and, in the same time, exhibits a high affinity to both, iron [77] and titanium [78], a formation
5 of the Fe-Si complexes in the bone tissue (Fig. 5) can be expected. Nevertheless, a more general
6 role of the bone silicon in the corrosion of metallic implants would require further targeted
7 investigation.
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13 **5. Summary and Conclusions**

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18 A selection of spectroscopy and electron microscopy techniques was employed in order to
19 characterize interfaces which were formed during 42 years of interaction between cortical
20 cranial bone and navigation screws made of AISI 304 stainless steel. Results of the
21 experimental analyses and simple numerical models suggest that the peri-implant bone layer
22 was subjected to an accelerated turnover with a characteristic period of about 3 years. The drop
23 in the period between consecutive remodelling events can be accounted for by an auto-catalytic
24 process in which the higher concentration of Fe^{n+} ions released from the implant stimulates the
25 osteoclast activity while the associated higher number of fresh resorption sites, in turn,
26 promotes the implant corrosion and enriches the IBL by a surplus of the Fe^{n+} ions. A comparison
27 of data acquired from the peri-implant bone (the interface bone layer IBL) and the cranial bone
28 situated far from the implant (distant bone DB) supports following main conclusions:
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- 40 1) The FTIR and Raman spectroscopy signals due to PO_4^{3-} groups increase along the path
41 from IBL towards DB.
- 42 2) The carbonate to phosphate ratio is lower while the organic to inorganic ration is higher
43 in the IBL. The Raman Pro peak was only detected in the IBL.
- 44 3) The XPS signal from silica is high and, consistent with the FTIR and Raman results, the
45 PO_4^{3-} peak is suppressed in the IBL.
- 46 4) SIMS measurements, TEM diffraction and high-resolution EDS independently detected
47 Fe-Si complexes in the IBL.
- 48 5) The high-resolution EDS analyses confirmed penetration of oxygen into the implant
49 surface where it forms up to 80 nm thick oxygen-enriched interface layers. This can be
50 primarily accounted for by a bio-corrosion associated with an acidic attack during
51 remodelling cycles.
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- 6) A presence of generally less aged tissue in the IBL would consistently rationalize experimental data and numerical results reported in the present study.

Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit author statement

Natália Luptáková: Investigation, Visualization, Writing - Original Draft **Václav Dlouhý:** Resources, Writing - Original Draft **Dinara Sobola:** Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Writing - Original Draft **Stanislava Fintová:** Investigation **Adam Weiser:** Investigation **Vladimír Beneš:** Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing **Antonín Dlouhý:** Conceptualization, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Writing - Original Draft.

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Table 1 Local chemical compositions (at%) of the steel screw and bone acquired by EDS during SEM and STEM observations.

Figure 1 Arrows in the CT images indicate positions in which the navigation screws rested for 42 years. Two bone layers namely Lamina externa (cortical) and Diploe (cancellous) hosted the metallic material. (a) Front view, (b) Side view, (c) Top view.

Figure 2 (a) A post-operation CT image documenting former locations of screws after their removal together with the surrounding bone. (b) A macroscopic view of the screw imbedded in the bone tissue after being explanted from the cranial bone. (c) Partially detached interfaces between bone and the screw, locations of a good adhesion are indicated by arrows, for further details see text.

Figure 3 Interface between AISI 304 steel and bone. (a) The circle indicates a location from where the STEM lamella was cut by FIB. (b) A detail showing the STEM lamella before a lift-up. See text for further details.

Figure 4 (a) Parts of the cortical cranial bone threaded in the steel screw, two rectangles (EDS 1 in the steel and EDS 2 in the bone) delimit areas from which the EDS signal was collected. The arrow indicates a resorption cavity. (b) EDS signal from the area EDS 1. (c) EDS signal from the area EDS 2.

Figure 5 ToF-SIMS maps showing distribution of elements in the transition region between the AISI 304 screw and the cranial bone. Regions 1 and 2 represent, respectively, a steel-bone overlap over the 750 nm thick slice and a bone volume with an increased concentration of iron and silicon. (a) True integrated signal. (b) Posterized signal, see text for further details.

Figure 6 Results of FTIR analysis. (a) The light microscopy image shows the cortical bone (dark area) embedded in one thread of the AISI screw (bright area). Three regions are delimited by circles: 1 - distant bone, 2 - osteon and 3 - peri-implant bone. (b) An intensity map of the integrated PO_4^{3-} peak ($960\text{-}1090\text{ cm}^{-1}$, see plot in c). (c) Spectral lines corresponding to positions 1, 2 and 3.

Figure 7 Results of Raman spectroscopy. (a) A blue rectangle in the light microscopy image marks the analysed area in the bone (dark contrast) and in one thread of the AISI screw (bright contrast). Three regions are delimited by small squares: region 1 - distant bone, region 2 - lacuna and region 3 - peri-implant bone. (b) An intensity map of integrated νIPO_4^{3-} peak (961 cm^{-1} , see plot in d). (c) An intensity map of the integrated Pro peak (814 cm^{-1} , see plot in d). (d) Spectral lines corresponding to positions 1, 2 and 3.

Figure 8 (a) STEM image of the FIBed lamella which covers the interface region between cranial bone and the AISI 304 steel screw. Positions of the SAD and EDS line experiments are indicated. (b) Experimental SAD1 from

the position 1 in the steel screw. (c) SAD1 complemented with JEMS-simulated diffraction rings (red). (d) Experimental SAD2 from the position 2 in the calcified bone. (e,f) SAD2 complemented with JEMS-simulated diffraction rings (red). (g) Experimental SAD3 from the position 3 in the uncalcified tissue. (h,i) SAD3 complemented with JEMS-simulated diffraction rings (red). See text for further details.

Figure 9 EDS line analyses taken across the bone-AISI implant interface. Positions of the individual lines are marked in Fig. 8a. (a) The line 1 samples chemical composition in a transition the implant and the calcified bone. (b) A zoom-in part of the EDS chart presented in a) which focuses only on the bone region. Correlations between Si and Fe signals are highlighted by double-headed arrows. (c) Chemical composition recorded along the line 2 taken through implant, calcified and uncalcified segments of the bone. (d) The same chart as in (c) which better reveals the Si/O ratio under the condition of the missing carbon signal.

Figure 10 Deconvolutions of the XPS peaks based on characteristic binding energies and corresponding chemical environments. (a, b) Si 2p XPS signal from (a) interface and (b) distant bone. (c, d) P 2p XPS signal from (c) interface and (d) distant bone.

Figure 11 Ferrous and ferric iron ions were detected in all the three locations investigated by the XPS technique: (a) explanted screw, (b) interface region and (c) peri-implant bone. After deconvolution, the Fe2p_{3/2} spectra show relative contributions of the individual ions and Fe-Si-O and Fe-O clusters.

Table 1 Local chemical compositions (at%) of the steel screw and bone acquired by EDS during SEM and STEM observations.

method	part	label/figure	C	Na	Mg	O	Si	P	Ca	Cr	Ni	Mn	Fe	Total
SEM/area	steel	EDS 1/Fig. 4	**	*	*	2.6	1.0	*	*	20.2	8.5	1.2	66.6	100.0
STEM/point	steel	EDS 3/**	**	*	*	1.6	1.0	0.1	0.0	19.8	8.5	0.9	68.1	100.0
STEM/point	steel	EDS 4/**	**	*	*	1.6	1.3	0.0	0.1	18.5	9.2	1.5	67.8	100.0
SEM/area	bone	EDS 2/Fig. 4	**	1.0	0.5	79.1	0.4	8.8	10.2	*	*	*	*	100.0
STEM/point	bone	EDS 5/**	**	0.0	0.6	83.2	1.4	9.4	4.4	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.8	100.0
STEM/point	bone	EDS 6/**	**	0.0	0.0	71.7	4.8	11.4	9.2	0.5	0.0	0.1	2.3	100.0

* not detected, ** excluded due to hydrocarbon contamination, *** figure not presented in this study